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CENTRING RAPE AND TRAUMA IN GORETTI KYOMUHENDO'S *SECRETS NO*

***MORE*¹**

East African Literary Criticism: Centering Rape and Trauma in Goretti Kyomuhendo's

Secrets no More

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Abstract

Criticisms of *Secrets no More* by Goretta Kyomuhendo need to unpack its considerable promises for greater visibility for female writers in Uganda and an enlarged scope of creative engagement for the East African literature in general. To this extent, corresponding critical attention need to be deployed to reinforce well-placed contentions, mediate critical attempts that grapples with the novel's unconventional narrativity, and inspire a need to locate and push other frontiers of knowledge of the "textual field".² The study will argue for a need to better appreciate *Secrets no More* as a piece of art that explores the genocide phase in the history of Rwanda with candour. It will aver that very much unlike many postcolonial African fictional narratives, the novel's strength is in its uniqueness of engagement with history in a way that readers' emotions and sensibilities are subjected to an unusual test of strength for confronting the reality of one of the most debased human conditions. The paper privileges a view of the history of the Rwandan genocide through the lenses of trauma and foregrounding of the peculiar emotional burden of a typical female victim of the genocide together with its aftermaths. This way, the study will present the novel as a major departure from a consistent narration of violence which dominated between 1969 and 1998 – a new form of writing which earned it an unmerited reductive assessment as a "vaginalist" creative addition to the East African literature.

²The idea of "textual field" -- an "open book" to which a wide range of perspectives may apply derives from Ellen Rooney. "Novel Reading". *Novel: A Forum on Fiction*, Vol.44, No.1. 2011, p27 and Remi Raji-Oyelade. "Notes Towards the Bibliography of Nigerian Women Poetry (1985-2006)" *Research in African Literature*. (39)1. 2008, p.59 respectively.

Introduction

An engagement with local issues sets *Secrets no More* (henceforth *Secrets*) by Goretti Kyomuhendo apart. Nevertheless, they are issues that resonate with global interest since they border on a large-scale collapse of social order and violation of the sanctity of human lives. This does not seem to be in contention as evident in the critiques on the novel available to the present writers. Published about a decade and half earlier than the influential essay of Mahfouz and Sultan on the East African literature, *Secrets* stands as a precursor to the essay in terms of how the essay proposes an ideal contemporary novel. In the brilliant essay, “The Situation of the Novel” a prediction on the future survival of the novel in the face of rapid social transformations that threaten its continued relevance – the authors emphasize the importance of continuing with the expression of “human nature and the social history of ongoing developments” within the enterprise of the novel. Doing this, they contend, will assure the social relevance of the novel and prevent its erasure from contemporary social history. They equally remark the possibility of a “fierce competition between local literature and world literature” as rapid advancement in technology promotes unrestricted accessibility to fictional narratives across different cultures of the world. A proposition of the essay is that *local issues should be kept as the focus in order to retain readership and assure the relevance of novelists* (Emphasis mine). Overall, the essay contends that there is a general decline in the popularity of the novel and classifies the cause as non-literary (Mahfouz and Sultan 46-47 :2005). Indeed, Mahfouz and Sultan’s study takes a global view of the novel.

To this wide extent, *Secrets*’ engagement with local issues should be recognized as outstanding in the light of *Secrets*’ six years of existence before the essay. . For obvious reasons, this pronouncement should not be taken for granted given the outstanding investment of

Mahfouz as a literature laureate, prolific novelist, and a critic. Sultan's literary standing, particularly as a critic of literature working in conjunction with the second literature laureate from Africa reinforces this in no mean way. It then befuddles that despite this weighty wider literary merit, *Secrets*' literary worth is contested on an East African literary standard. For engaging with issues of the historical genocide in Rwanda, its sociological worth is arguably top rate.

Granted that *Secrets* is of such an enormous worth, a rather reductive assessment of it in the collection of criticisms of the novel informs the present study. It is interesting that the particular criticism under focus is of East African origin, Uganda to be specific – the very nationality of the author. *Secrets* is taken for a vaginalist narrative despite that it could be considered an effective engagement with local issues to which global attention has been significantly attracted. One could therefore ask: should the faculty of criticism of the novel not be unsettled by such “assignation of value”, to borrow a term from (Alonso 3 :2011), to an author based on a reading of an author and her/his work as one and the same? The study contends that Kyomuhendo is at best an indirect victim of what in Winter's opinion, is negative prejudice derived from “unthinking prejudgments based on custom or habit” with a concomitant “negative social bias against persons or categories of people”. Hence, this paper will align with Winter's summation (176: 2010) of such a prejudicial mode of assessment: reducing reasoning to dimensions of the box of history's episteme or teasing out fresh proposition based on a critic's tradition-based knowledge production system. Based on such an alignment, the paper aims to inspire further readings of Kyomuhendo and her work by underscoring the critical importance of transcending the kind of prejudice leading to evaluating the novel and its author in vaginalist terms.

Kyomuhendo is characterized as a “vaginalist” on account of some sexually explicit bits of her narrative. This is a good instance of such prejudicial criticism as Bernt (223: 2009) has helped to show. For Berndt, Kyomuhendo’s “candid exploration of such taboo subjects as sexual violence and female sexuality” is the reason she is so characterized. As deeply informing as the Bernt’s remark is, it need be countenanced alongside other tropes that are by far of greater narrative attention within the same textual framework than those based on which the vaginalist classification of *Secrets* is done. In other words, while it may be true that an exploration of “sexual violence and female sexuality” might sharply offend the sensibility of critics that are disinclined towards unrestrictive imaginative reconstruction of such a genocidal incident, the defence needs to fully unpack the burden of the allegation of being vaginalist. If, as Kyomuhendo claims and may be deciphered, her works are borne out of empathy, she might as well deserve empathy. This is because one might need, at least for a moment, to imagine oneself in her shoes and wonder as she does during the interview she granted Gray as to why her own narrative style should be questioned. Gray had put it to her frontally: “But some of your scenes are extremely graphic and violent”, and she reacted:

Yes, there are rape scenes, described very harshly, and also sex scenes, which are intentionally described very accurately, because I kept saying: African women are not meant to enjoy sex, on the one hand, or be wounded by it on the other. Any pleasure, or any pain, is to be kept quiet. So I wrote about those things very openly. Unfortunately, some people take these scenes out of context, and the work gets read for the wrong reasons. But you get sex scenes in

the male writers too, and nobody ever considers them obscene
(Gray 125: 2001).³

It is very difficult to take her response as satisfactory enough though. This is because we are taken through her exposition only to emerge more worried by such contention shared among the folks chosen for representation in the novel that women's attainment of sexual pleasure or denial of it under sexual abuse should be kept quiet. This, as she reveals in the interview, is why "extremely graphic and violent" sexual scenes are so presented in the novel.

However, about two years later, Kyomuhendo, addresses the issue of her creative drive and vision regarding *Secrets*. It is very clear *Secrets* is ideologically informed and the narrative audacity for which the novel is condemned is a sign of her orientation as a member of FEMRITE – Ugandan Women Writers Association – and practical reflection of the body's ideological focus. This focus is essentially political. Her statement on the role of the women body in the politics of literature in Uganda reveals it all:

As a literary association committed to women's freedom of expression, we have realized that women often refrain from telling the stories in their hearts. Many women think of themselves as wives, mothers or daughters, and when they write, they concentrate on the feelings and reactions of others, rather than their own. Very often, anxiety and fear about how a story will be perceived precedes the need to tell a good story.

³ At the interview conducted with her by the first of the present writers in 2018, her worries remained laden with emotion.

Her underscoring of the foregoing with a recount of one of FEMRITE member's experience is worthy of note too. The member had composed "an extremely evocative story using the first-person narrative mode" but had to discard it because her husband "objected strongly to the use of the first person in such a line as 'I was raped on my wedding night'⁴. The husband, Kyomuhendo reports, had reasoned that his wife might be taken for the rape victim being depicted. Consequently, the FEMRITE member had to change the narrative voice thus, reducing the impact of the story.. A workshop of FEMRITE, she added, had prepared members for challenges of social inhibitions and "ingrained cultural beliefs" and that focus should rather be on the self (23: 2003).

On this count, therefore, we choose to reinforce Berndt's simple but powerful defence of Kyomuhendo in the foregoing in fully unpacking the burden of properly reading the novel. We propose that the features of the narrative so ideologically identified and isolated for criticism be married to others yet to be equally foregrounded within the template of perception of Kyomuhendo as some sort of radical feminist ideologue. This may be necessary because the African Novel is not known yet for entertaining what Ercolino (241-256: 2012) identifies with the novel in such climes as Europe and America as "inflation of discourse" such that could make the African Novel give considerable narrative prominence to multivalent issues as embodied in *Secret*. Hence the African Novel, it should be noted, remains a storehouse of silent but crucial disclosures on contemporary African progression through history.

Indeed, as an avowed feminist writer, critic and activist, Kyomuhendo informs that she endeavours to foreground "female characters" and "trivialities" that afflict womenfolk" to enrich society's understanding and drive appreciation of females' peculiarities in her works (23: 2003).

⁴ An extract from the interview conducted with Kyomuhendo by the first of the paper's authors.

This is telling enough for the reader to sense that her writing is as subsumed by much broader sociological concerns as it is distinguished by her gender sensitivity. All she does is to strive to secure for her female gender a place central enough for their visibility in her mirroring of society at large. In reasoning this way, how her works have been read so far, especially *Secrets* that has been singled out for classification as vaginalsit, deserves to be complemented with new reading and highlight of ways in which her works may be further appreciated. This is because what should matter ultimately regarding how she and/or her works are perceived is the aggregate of critical opinions on both sides of literary criticism. And because she represents a prominent actor on the contemporary East African literary scene, what is needed, as more attempts to fulfil the desire for criticisms that “limns collectively”, to borrow a phrase from Waliula (188: 2012), the East African literature , is a deeper exploration of what the literature of the region has encouragingly churned out. The present reading seeks to achieve this through “counter-evidence, concerted mental retraining, and the activation of the just conscience” a fascinating critical parameter proposed by Winter though in respect of the Anglophone Novel (177 :2010).

For emphasis, and because insights from Winter postulations on the novel serve our present reading quite positively, we note: *Secrets* does fit into the novel of prejudice because it meets the criteria by which Winter has set this category apart: successions of “epistemological reflections and ethical transactions that the reader is meant to consider and practice in a reasoned fashion—as lesson learned or a new perspective gained” (177). The proposition which this paper pushes therefore amounts to the stated challenge that which a reader might encounter on the kind of “textual field” that Rooney (27 :2011) contends the novel represents.

It is on this note the present reading of *Secrets*, which by all standards is representative of Kyomuhendo’s sustained creative career that has been prejudicially evaluated in certain regard,

shall proceed. This will be by way of extracting from the novel's creative framework a quantum of historical reconstruction of the Rwandan genocide alongside experiences of human degradation that attended it as Uganda became a receptor space for Rwandan refugees in the aftermath of the genocide. This way, the paper hopes to properly dissect the narrative of possibility of hope woven around one individual character in the novel's imaginative framework of engagement with the history from one of its most harrowing dimensions. As the novel suggests in a broader sense of interlocking and variegated social experiences of Marina, the protagonist of the novel, there could still have been what Nazareth (351 :2000) describes as "possibility of redemption" despite the extreme violence in Rwanda and the consequent exploitative tendencies in Uganda that combine to form the core of Marina's life, Marina emerges a crucial redemptive agency. This way, *secrets* will be shown to be a creative precursor of Alonso's critical comment that literature is

an immanent succession of works in time, as the transhistorical truths about the human condition, as a discourse that reveals the ambivalent nature of language, or as a cultural horizon that necessarily engages reality from a critical perspective(3: 2011)

Like others African fictions inspired by philosophy of hope for the shredded Africa, *Secrets* is not just demonstrating the promise of hope for humanity and progressive transformation of humans which Doody (154: 2009) contends the novel genre shares with philosophy.

Historical Schema and Trauma

Going by one of the adopted definitions of the United States-based Historical Novel Society, as reported by Rodwell (47: 2013), which de-emphasizes the age of the writing of a novel and foregrounds qualities that make a novel an “alternative history”, Gray and Kyomuhendo’s (137: 2001) assessment of *Secrets* is well-placed. Both contend that *Secrets* is a historical novel which draws on the Rwandan genocide as it features selected experiences of a girl-child victim of the genocide to draw the attention of readers to a humongous carnage in human history. Nevertheless, for them, it falls into a fictional narrative category that foregrounds certain vital aspects of life of the African female which are best handled by a fellow female. On this, they reason that females would be better placed to relate to such experiences because of shared gender. While the gender of an author may not necessarily matter in evaluating an author’s work, where a particular authorial intervention is seen to be necessary for evaluation may not be discounted. It is on this count we propose that *Secrets* will be better evaluated when its ideological coming-into-being is downplayed to the advantage of the historical and social circumstances that inspired its formulation. This way, *Secrets* can then be taken to mean an “alternative history” as Dipio (41-45 :2011) endeavours to show. Based on the disclosure made by Kyomuhendo about *Secrets* and Dipio’s characterisation of *Secrets* as a narrative told as an alternative to “official history”, *Secrets* can be better received as a site of historical reconstruction with an account of attendant trauma.

Taking as an alternative history, its primary feature should be boldly marked. It is such an alternative history that has been refashioned in line with the essential criteria by which the African Novel is distinguished as highlighted by Sullivan (177-188 :2006): meeting the readers’ interest, and cultural requirements, and being representative of the African peculiar ways of literary practice. And because the “typical African on the African continent occupies a most horrible spot on the global space because of experiences of monstrosities in spite of modern

civilization, the African novel can really present a bewildering alternative history.”⁵To appreciate *Secrets* in the context it is being presently situated against the backdrop of what we arguably uphold as its unfavourable criticism and the attendant underselling of the author, what Martin reports as the “ethical dilemma of representing trauma,” is important for the kind of understanding being sought for the novel. As Martin explains, what is essential in representations bordering on trauma lies in the contentious issue of choice between ability to represent and desirability of representation lexically marked by “can” and “should” respectively. Hence, the writer carries the burden of the ethical obligation of either making a cure or poison of her/his writing; this is because her/his writing on trauma can either “reactivate the original trauma” or serve as a “release and [potential healing]” for society (191: 2014).

Through this insightful exposition of the ethical obligation of the novelist preoccupied with issues of trauma, Kyomuhendo’s ability to represent the experience of trauma, using a girl-child of Rwandan origin whose life history proceeds from being a freeborn through being a refugee to being an adult resident in Uganda with the challenge of complicated identity to contend with, may not be as important as her audacious representation of a genocide-induced trauma. For being daring alone, Kyomuhendo fulfils the ethical requirement, which is never necessarily deserving of credit on the basis of being capable to dare. As we shall subsequently do an evaluation of her creative engagement with history and trauma, we might need to insist that criticism must no longer be seen as revelling in the dustbin of history of the novel to which the denial of women’s access to the pleasure of the novel, as Van (159 :2010) reports, has long been cast. Critics, on either side of the arena of judgment on the novel genre, should therefore be guided by the peculiar nature of the genre itself which, as Bewes (18 :2011) indicates, is in its

⁵ Naguib Mahfouz and Sabbar S. Sultan. “The Situation of the Novel” *World Literature Today*. Vol. 79, No. 2 (2005): 46-47

being a “technical” problematic rather than an “ethical” one. This point might come out clearer as the paper attempts to show how history is imaged as a broader human phenomenon encompassing trauma on the one hand, and trauma of a girl-child victim of an ethnically engendered genocide within a postcolonial geopolitical entity is imaged, on the other hand.

Imaging History and Trauma

“Why image at all?” Rae asks while introducing the importance of this act and the process it entails. “Imaging”, he defines, “is a process that gives us access to a part of our brain that we infrequently use in a conscious way. Through imaging”, he explains, “we can come to know more about this realm of inner space, which has been shut off from us—about its powers and its limits—because imaging is a key that opens a door into what has been called the unconscious mind” (155 :1985). Given the year of publication of his essay “ETC: A Review of General Semantics”, this notion of the unconscious which Rae explicates might not have taken cognizance of the possibility of the kind of thinking over three decades later by which the understanding of the concept may be said to have been deepened. The latter conception of the notion persuades beyond the “conscious-centric” tendency by which the unconscious is reduced to the “subliminal” in cognitive psychology in the original conception of the idea. For the present purpose, the significance of imaging to representation of experiences is key. One might only therefore avoid the enormous burden of technicalities involved in cognitive psychology and cognate disciplines to which cognitive psychology shares common interest in respect of how the unconscious may be critically understood. Besides, what is of interest to the present study is the idea of imaging history and trauma as features of human reality characterized by a subsuming of one by the other and phases of understanding human reality that might require being separated in evaluative contexts. And because Rae’s discourse of this comes within the purview of

semantics—an enterprise dealing with meaning in relation to language by which literature as a communicative act is set in motion, Rae’s most apt illustration of the concept of image will be centered:

Most of us, when we come across a descriptive passage in a book, do more than read it. We experience it. We crawl into the world created by the author and live in it as we would in our own -all senses operating. We see and hear and smell and touch without any direct input from the external world to our senses, and even though we may not do it well, we can learn to do it better. But why would we want to do it better? Aside from reading fiction or listening to a storyteller, what's the point in this conjuring up or imagin-ing?

(Bargh and Morsella 155: 2008)

Perhaps the novel’s dual or, rather, bifurcated concerns might be better grasped in the manner in which Mamdani (xiii :2001) gained instantaneous comprehension of the genocidal incident and its attendant consequences: “that just because the genocide took place within the boundaries of Rwanda, it did not mean that either the dynamics that led to it or the dynamics it unleashed in turn were confined to Rwanda”. The full dimensions of the agony of Marina as the novel’s main communicative medium might not be captured if they are not measured against the background of the historical incident that stimulated the idea of the novel. In doing this, we might be able to gain deeper insight into the novel’s alternative historical account on the Rwandan genocide and its immediate transnational consequences partly but significantly exemplified by Uganda’s intervention by default as a major unofficial asylum for Rwandan refugees. Nonetheless, perhaps the focus on Marina might need to be queried to determine the

novel's leaning in terms of the options freely available to African writers in the novel genre between the Western tradition of fiction writing marked by a sustained focus on the individual and the African literary tradition of yielding African literature to the sociology of Africa. Kyomuhendo's identitarian preferences are clearly African even as her messages in *Secrets* bear a transracial coloration. Her activism is avowedly Uganda-based, determinedly sexist in the sense that the African female intellectual must be allowed visibility and unrestricted opportunity to act on the literary intellectual stage like her male counterpart, particularly regarding the East African literature.

Reading *Secrets* as a single individual story might privilege an evaluation of the novel as “virginalist” and lead to a shift of attention from the sociological framework of the African novel which *Secrets* does not fail to key into. However, by weaving the two experiences of rape of Marina to the “silent disclosures” on those traumatic experiences, access to full dimensions to her agony is granted. Therefore, she is not just a helpless onlooker of the nauseating rape of her mother in a circumstance of social upheaval within one ethnically warring geopolitically space but a direct victim of rape at a peaceful corner of another geopolitical space devoid of similar or the same monumental social upheaval climaxed by carnage. Attention should hence shift to the larger African social context that the narrative should be stressed to address as a reinforcement of the sociological agency of African literature. The novel then throws in full relief the issue of vulnerability of the African girl-child in circumstances of harrowing experience of sudden and horrific separation from her very lovely family, the horrors of war-induced displacement, and the feebleness of intervention offered voluntarily by a theocratic care-giving agency represented in Father Marcel.

Worthy of note is the fact that the two rape cases are not presented in equal breadth, except in terms of narrative details which make the blame in each case appear partly because of natural temptation rather than a consequence of emotion of deep-seated hate for another on the other side of the ethnic divide. In fact, the narrative details of the rape of Marina which apports the blame of the wrong to Matayo and alcohol fail in reinforcing the monstrosity in which rape of Marina is cast Here is an account of Marina's mother experience of rape as provided by Kyomuhendo:

“She was spread-eagled on the floor with two soldiers holding her down. A giant of a soldier was towering over her, consciously rubbing his manhood which was slowly forming a bulge in his trousers. He wore a stupid victorious grin and kept on licking his lips [...] the colonel struggled out of his trousers and stood there naked, his manhood obscenely pointing in front of him. In one swift movement, he was on top of Mukundane. She put up a feeble resistance but she might as well have reserved her energy. The two soldiers holding her down were too strong for her [...] the colonel, with a vicious thrust of his body, entered her [...] Mukundane tried to push the Colonel away but only succeeded in igniting him more. Like a possessed man, he began pounding at her. He slowed down briefly and looked in Bizimana's direction. [...] With renewed energy, the Colonel resumed the pounding. Mukundane curled her fingers into claws and lashed out at him. [...] Mukundane screamed out as the colonel seemed to tear at her insides (17: 1999).

Marina's account is only a little longer:

“He pinned her to the ground, then with one arm, he began unzipping his trousers. In one swift movement, Matayo had removed the trousers and was trying to part Marina’s thighs, using his legs. Marina then knew what Matayo intended to do to her. “No, no,” Marina began screaming and tried to put up a fight. But she was too feeble to ward him off. Images of her mother, spread-eagled on the floor and the Colonel on top of her, flashed through her mind. She also remembered the agony-filled sounds her mother had made. Matayo was holding his elongated stiff manhood in one hand, while he used the other hand to keep Marina pinned to the ground. He began forcing himself inside her. Marina felt an excruciating pain tear through her body as Matayo entered her. He pumped at her and probed inside her with his enormous manhood. His torso was jerking up and down, establishing a consistent rhythm. Marina began to whimper in a low tone. Matayo’s mouth quickly closed over hers and he began kissing her, drawing the air out of her lungs. He thrust his manhood deeper inside her with renewed vigour. Marina cried out in pain and once again tried to push Matayo off her body but Matayo was making animal sounds and his eyes were closed. He gave one last, hard thrust inside her before he withdrew. His heavy body remained on top of Marina for a while and he continued heaving and breathing fast. Marina laid there, all energy drained out of her. Eventually, when she managed to push Matayo’s bulk off her, her first thought was that her private parts were torn out because she felt a lot of pain down there. She touched them gingerly, they were covered with a warm sticky liquid” (58-59).

It interests to remark a noticeable narrative gap between the account of Marina’s mother’s rape experience and Marina’s. This is better explained in terms of the grammatical patterning of the former and the latter as they coincide and diverge. The range of words suggests a conscious grammatical demarcation between the two accounts. In both accounts, ‘spread-eagle’, ‘feeble’,

‘manhood’, ‘holding her down’, and ‘pinned to the ground’ are used to account for two separate, but connected, coterminous and contiguous experiences of trauma in a single human existence – Marina’s.

Indeed, imaging the monstrosity that marked historical progression of the ethnically divided post-independent Rwanda and the trauma it bears should make a centre point of criticism regarding *Secrets*. This point is not lost on the author. And it is significant to note that authorial pronouncement helps in this wise. Kyomuhendo excuses herself from being a virginalist, which suggests her disinclination towards reading her novel in such an isolation. But it would appear commonplace that a writer’s subjects of interest might be graded based on the narrative attention or details given to each subject within an entire narrative frame. If, as Kyomuhendo argues, her interest should not be measured by the specific narrative details of the rape incidents, it might be asked what exactly are we to pay attention to?” If those who read vaginalism into the novel have their claims supported by the breadth of the narrative assigned the rape events as the case is, could they still be inclined to characterise the same novel as a narrative in service of Christian theological advancement, since given this vaginalism is not as dominant a motif as Christian theology in the novel’s representational schema;

No less relevant is the narrative attention given to Rosaria’s amusing innocence before the kid’s reunion with her mother, Marina. The whole Chapters One and Two of Part Three are devoted to it. Apart from the foregoing two ‘scatological’ accounts, there is a third account in the category on how George’s admired lady, Lisa, is caught in the sex act with George’s gateman. On the contrary, it is not given a comparably sustained narrative attention (Kyomuhendo 114: 1999) like (i) and (ii). Might we then argue that the author seems not to be as inclined to provide the details of the illicit sexual act, perhaps because it has not the kind of pity-evoking trauma as the earlier

two sexual scenes with very comparatively more traumatic effect? If this could serve in critical evaluation, and of course it should, then there is more to insertion of sexual episodes as a narrative element of *Secrets*. This is why it might be needed to shift critical attention away from the episodes foregrounding sex to the weighty sociologically thematics of the narrative where reading provokes ‘why’ repeatedly in interrogating the entire traumatic history and its breakdown into traumatic episodes of rape of mother and child, and the contiguity of both experience in one innocent being.

From the foregoing, there is a lot to appreciate about Nabutanyi’s joint assessment of *Secrets* and two short stories ‘Luxurious Hearses’ and ‘My Parents’ Bedroom’ selected from Uwem Akpan’s collection of short stories, *Say You’re One of Them*. *Secrets* like others in his critical purview, he observes, ‘employs strategies that evoke affect and offer implicit analyses of children’s experiences of genocide and mass violence’. While, for Nabutanyi, the accusation of vaginalism levelled against Kyomuhendo might not constitute a major critical issue, his emphasis that *Secrets* is no less than a narrative of “genocide and mass violence” that foregrounds a ‘[child victim, witness, and survivor]’ to the horrendous experiences is equally noteworthy. His reading of the novel:

I pay attention to affective passages that encourage our empathetic identification with the experiences of the child victim and/or survivor. The emotive power of [this] narrative provides us with insights into the causes and nature of genocide and mass violence in Africa in non-explicit ways. Such implicit analysis, I argue, advances more nuanced responses to question such as why, how, or by whose agency genocide and mass violence comes about

and/or what characterizes it. These narratives enable[s] us to establish an intimate awareness of the represented world, refusing us the ‘comfortable position of distant observation. The [text] encourage, instead, identification and deeper engagement with the atrocities narrated. (101-102: 2014)

If the foregoing provides clarity that the novel embodies representations of genocide and mass violence – an inward reading of the novel, so to state – Kiyimba’s (2008) reading is the opposite. The significance of placing the novel’s overall thematic totality within the context of the dynamics of gender consciousness that shape the Uganda writing tradition is a fulcrum of Kiyimba’s reading to be subsequently cited. Ugandan women writers have abdicated their former role as the ‘hen’ because they also desire to ‘crow’ like the cock.

The significant place of conscious artistic ideology is worth noting here. Measured against this background, *Secrets* will attest Kyomuhendo as belonging in an agency that pushes for expansion of opportunity for the Ugandan women writers to function on equal footing with their male counterparts. This fact is not as important as the very crucial culturally subversive style of deliberate insertion of sexually explicit episodes which prejudicial vaginalist parameter may not capture. This is because such an “outsider perspective” is incapable to measure the considerable extent to which the novel should be seen to “[bear] witness to trauma” as Samuel (3 :2010) contends in regard to three outstanding creative works on the Rwandan genocide and its

aftermath: *Inyenzi: A Story of Love and Genocide* (novel), *Murambi, The Book of Bones* (novel) and *Shooting Dogs* (film).⁶

Marked Transition

From the 70s when Githire reports that Taban lo Liyong regrettably identified the whole of East Africa as a “sterile literary scene” and over two decades after when *Secrets* appeared on the East African literary scene in an astounding manner, there had been a lack of creative engagement of crucial social events despite the wide latitude presented by the historical progression of the region in turmoil. Liyong, as reported by Githre again, had lamented in 1999 (182: 2010). The year of this second lament is significant for the present study because it coincided with the year *Secrets* made its astounding appearance on the East African literary scene. If the novel makes any impact in the literary history of East Africa in terms of transition from a barren field to a literary spectacle of some sort, the transition deserves to be accounted for in terms of the far distance between lament over regional literary bareness and a repugnant reception of a single case of upstage succeeding the era of bareness—*Secrets*. Against the background of cultural inhibition such as recognized and confronted by FEMRITE, the vaginalist ascription to the novel cannot be as serious as what the ascription means for the national and regional reception of the novel. This must be taken up boldly and consistently so as to spur the trend of transition from where *Secrets* has infused the Ugandan Literary history and the larger history of the East African literature with a dose of radical self-reflectivity to a much desired visibility on the continental literary stage. As a forewarning, critical reception of the East African literature—nationally or regionally—should anticipate lots of border-crossing and subversiveness in literary representation of society. That is clear in the agency that FEMRITE

⁶ Karin Samuel, “Bearing Witness to Trauma: Representations of the Rwanda Genocide”. Unpublished Thesis, Stellenbosch University, 2010.

represents and the credit that goes to FEMRITE by the publication of the novel and the stir it has provoked within the little space of its critical reception and considerably larger space of public reception, especially in Uganda.

Kiyimba (133 :1998) calls attention to a tendency in the Ugandan novel: devotion to the “description of the sexual exploits of the real-life Amin and affirms the visibility of the tendency across other major Ugandan novels, namely “*The Silent Rebel, The Floods, The Seasons of Thomas Tebo, Bitter Harvest*, among others”. It is noteworthy that the four novels are male-authored and each is marked by exploitation of sexual experience as motif. This is the larger context of criticism of Ugandan fiction that should provide a background against which *Secrets* should be more satisfactorily appreciated. Bits of records on the contemporary Uganda literature have it that male writers enjoy very wide (almost unlimited?) latitude to represent sexuality as they deem fit without social and/or cultural restraints.

Conclusion

Indeed, *Secrets* shares semblance with *Waiting*—another novel of Kyomuhendo following up on Spencer’s observation. This is in view of what Spencer has indicated to be a consistent pattern of “reflecting on the lived experiences of the individual” and representing “violence and the disintegration of the home” (109: 2015) maintained by Kyomuhendo. However, where *Secrets* is to be most rated is in its full compliance with four parameters of war time literature on rape as clearly outlined in the study of Isikozlu and Millard (35-36 :2018): identification of “modalities of wartime rape”; “exploring effects of wartime rape alongside the physical and psychological consequences”; and “understanding the cultural context in which the rape took place”. Following their expert classifications of wartime rape, *Secrets* represents incidents based on an “intra-state” war characterized by “ethnic cleansing and genocide”. Overall, in a range of literary productions

of Kyomuhendo capturing the first three novels of Kyomuhendo: *The First Daughter*, *Secrets* and *Waiting*, a consistent pattern of representing a girl-child heroine is maintained. This a clear creative schema that has come to define Kyomuhendo's literary career. Within the schema, *Secrets* somewhat marks a crescendo where the East African literature may be said to have a major contribution to the discourse of rape as a feature of war. To its utmost credit, the novel, as if in conscious anticipation of the need to avoid the usual emphasis on representation of mass rape, attains a high level of clarity by focusing one single line of occurrence by which the statement of the trauma of wartime rape is made with tremendous effect. The significance of this should be noted in a dominant manner in which rape is reported to have been represented and the need to transit from such a manner of representation:

[...] the emphasis placed on mass rape could be problematic because it suggests that rape must occur on a large scale in order to be a visible and prosecutable crime. There are indeed cases of rape that are not perpetrated in a systematic fashion, but which are no less problematic. An emphasis on mass rape also obscures individual experiences of wartime rape and the variation in which these violations are both perpetrated against and interpreted by the individual (36)

Following further from the study of Isikozlu and Millard, could it be the case that “rape is essentially an expression of a socially and culturally engrained hatred by men of all women”? Could it be that, after all, *Secrets*, only uses the two rape incidents in the novel to alert us over a long overlooked area of hatred for women—“an act of misogyny, not sexuality [...] not an aggressive expression of sexuality, but a sexual expression of aggression”?(36). *Secrets* opens

the floor for debate beyond Thornhill's various biological explanations on the inner promptings of men who rape (137-148 1999:). It invites the reader to a postcolonial African situation in which circumstances of rape and victims of rape accentuate the need to clamour for proper African socio-political reconstitution in the postcolonial phase of her history.

Primary Text

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